

A NOVEL APPROACH FOR HYBRID BONDED REPAIR OF PRIMARY METALLIC STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

A hybrid repair solution combining a stress optimised cut-out and a bonded patch is an effective approach for primary structure repairs, in which the optimised cut-out enhances the residual strength to meet certification requirement while the bonded patch provides further stress reduction in the repaired structure and achieve significant additional fatigue life enhancement. In this study, a cracked specimen was repaired with an optimised cut-out at the crack tip and two boron/epoxy patches bonded back-to-back. The patches were positioned adjacent and some distance away from the cut-out and thus potential crack re-occurrence/growth can be visually monitored without the patch concealing the area. The effectiveness of the hybrid repair was assessed experimentally by comparing to three other specimen configurations namely specimens with a crack, a standard stop drill at the crack tip, and an optimum cut-out hole at the crack tip.

Finite element modelling results indicated that compared with the standard stop-hole specimen, the stress concentration factors of the specimens with optimum cut-out hole and hybrid repairs were reduced by 63% and 73%, respectively. Based on a simple cubic law, these stress reductions would result in the fatigue life before crack re-initiation to be 20 and 52 times longer. Fatigue tests under variable amplitude loads confirmed the significant extension of fatigue initiation life, where 28 and 53 times of enhancement were achieved for the optimum cut-out hole and hybrid repairs, respectively. The fatigue test results further showed that for the stop drill and optimum cut-out configurations, once the crack was reinitiated, its growth was relatively fast, whilst in the case of the specimen with the hybrid repair the crack growth rate was significantly slower.

1 INTRODUCTION

Adhesively bonded patch repair has been applied to many metallic primary aircraft structures in the past and it is generally appreciated that this repair has many advantages over a repair based on mechanical fastening. However, difficulties in meeting some of the certification requirements have limited further applications of bonded repairs on aircraft primary structures [1-3]. The main obstacles are that current quality control and Non Destructive Inspection procedures that can feasibly be applied to bonded repairs (undertaken in non-ideal situations) cannot ensure sufficient reliability for initial and ongoing bond integrity. Thus, at present, bonded repairs can only be applied to those primary structures suffering cracks or damage where the residual strength clearly exceeds design limit load prior to application of the bonded repair. Defence Science and Technology Group (DST Group) has developed a research roadmap for bonded repairs on primary structures. One key component is to

develop hybrid repair approaches to meet certification requirements via enhancement of residual strength (Figure 1) through optimum damage removal and adding alternative load paths [1-4]. DST Group and its partner organisations have carried out a series of research and development programs in this area [4-11]. A particular hybrid repair method will be presented in this paper.

A stop hole is often used as a temporary measure to resist fatigue crack propagation in metallic structures. The effect of the stop hole is generally rather limited. A crack often soon re-occurs due to the relatively high stress at the stop hole. A much more effective option is to cold expand the hole (for example with an oversized fastener) to develop compressive stresses around the hole and at the tip of any residual crack. However, crack growth will be very rapid if re-initiation occurs.

A stress optimised stop hole (or other forms of damage cut out) achieved through shape optimisation may significantly reduce the stress concentration at the damage crack tip [12]. This repair method may be certified to extend the fatigue life of cracked structures. However, the fatigue life enhancement from a stress optimised cut-out alone could still be limited and the crack growth would also be rapid if re-initiation occurs. A hybrid repair solution combining a stress optimised cut-out and a bonded patch would provide significant further fatigue life enhancement.

DUL – Design Ultimate Load DLL = Design Limited Load

Figure 1. Illustration of strength enhancement prior to application of bonded patch repair

DST Group and its research partners have considered three different patch configurations in these hybrid repair approaches, namely (i) the patch is positioned over the optimised damage cut-out, (ii) the patch surrounds the optimised damage cut-out, and (iii) the patch is positioned adjacent and some distance away from the optimised cut-out, refer to Figure 2.

Figure 2. Illustration of damage and repair configurations. (a) to (e) for edge crack; (f) and (g) for non-edge crack.

The research programs using the above first two patch configurations were presented in References [10] and [11], respectively. The research program using the third patch configuration is described in this paper. Similar to the patch configuration where the patch surrounds the optimised damage cut-out [11], this patch reinforcement configuration has several features: i) the bonded patch helps reduce the stress at the damage/high stress region through load bypass; ii) the patch rigidity does not have to match the parent structure and the level of stress reduction can be controlled by adjusting the patch thickness, and iii) adhesive failure as a critical failure mode can be eliminated. In addition, potential crack re-occurrence/ growth in the parent structure can be monitored without the patch concealing the area.

The idea to attach bonded patches beside the damage cut-out or potential crack development area has been adopted in many applications [13–16]. Figure 3 shows a bonded patch design described in Reference [14], where two patches with shapes generated from a shape optimisation algorithm redirected the load away from the highly stressed hole edge. DST Group and its research partners adopted a similar but significantly simplified design for repair of a composite helicopter spar by bonding two rectangular patches at each side of the hole [16].

Figure 3. Optimal patch geometry for the tensile test specimen reported in Reference [14]. (a) Optimized patch shape and (b) Von Mises stress profile.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Experiment

Four types of specimens were considered, shown in Figure 4 (corresponding to Figure 2a, b, c and e). They included a specimen with a crack, a specimen with a crack and a standard (3 mm diameter circular) stop hole at the crack tip, a specimen with a crack and an optimum cut-out hole, and a specimen with a crack and an optimum cut-out hole plus two boron/epoxy patches bonded back-to-back (hybrid repair).

The specimens were cut from 7075 T6 aluminium alloy plate, to a dimension of 380 x 100 x 6.35 mm (Figure 5). The patch was made using boron/epoxy 5521/4 unidirectional prepreg with $[0_6]$ layup and FM300-2k film adhesive.

For the cracked specimens, an initial 12mm slit cut by electrical discharge machining was pre-cracked 8 mm under constant fatigue loading to achieve a 20mm crack tip from the specimen edge. For the specimens with cut-outs the length from the specimen edge to the hole edge was 20 mm (Figure 5).

Figure 4: Four specimen configurations – cracked and different repair configurations.

Figure 5. Test specimen with optimum cut-out and bonded patches (dimension in mm)

The patches were manufactured first, with a co-cured layer of FM300-2K allowing easier surface preparation and subsequent bonding to the parent aluminium specimen. Manufacturer recommended curing cycle for FM300-2k (121°C 120 minutes) was applied.

Standard DST Group grit-blast/silane surface treatment procedure applied to aluminium plates included:

- Scotch Brite abrasion;
- MEK solvent clean ;
- Grit-blast under specified conditions;
- Application of coupling agent (silane A-187)

The patches were bonded to aluminium plates using another layer of FM300-2k, cured in autoclave.

The test was conducted on an Instron tensile test machine. A uniaxial varied amplitude spectrum fatigue load was applied with the peak load of 76.8 kN (121 MPa remote stress). The detailed spectrum was described in [17]. Crack growth was monitored using a pair of digital cameras and measured by image metrology.

2.2 Modelling

The shape optimisation approach described in Reference [12] was used to design the hole shape. Referring to Figure 6, the hole profile coordinates (x, y) were defined using the following formulae:

$$x = R[(1 + m)\cos(\theta) - n\cos(3\theta)] \quad (1)$$

$$y = R[(1 - m)\sin(\theta) + n\sin(3\theta)] \quad (2)$$

where

$$m = (1 - n)\frac{(l - 1)}{(l + 1)} \quad (3)$$

$$R = a/[1 + m - n] \quad (4)$$

and l is the hole's aspect ratio, $l = a/b$, and a and b are the lengths of the hole's semi-major axis and semi-minor axis respectively. In this repair design the parameters used are: $a = 13.5$, $b = 5.4$, $m = 0.4337$ and $n = -0.002$.

A 3-dimensional MSC/Nastran finite element model was constructed. The material property data used are listed in Table 1.

G939 Prepreg			FM300 Adhesive			7075 T6 aluminium		
Property	Type	Value	Property	Type	Value	Property	Type	Value
Modulus (GPa)	$E11$	210	Shear modulus	G	46	Modulus	E	71.7
	$E22$	19						
	$E33$	19						
	$G12$	6.89						
	$G13$	6.89						
Poisson Ratio	$G23$	6.89	Poisson Ratio	λ	0.35	Poisson Ratio	λ	0.33
	$\lambda12$	0.21						
	$\lambda13$	0.21						
Strength (MPa)	$\lambda23$	0.30	Shear yield stress	τ_p	480.2	Yield Strength (MPa)	σ_y	503
	$\sigma11$	1520						
	$\sigma22$	48.3						
	$\sigma33$	48.3						
	$\tau12$	103						
Thickness (mm)	$\tau13$	103	Shear failure strain	γ_{ult}	0.19			
	$\tau23$	103						
Thickness (mm)		0.13	Thickness (mm)		0.15			

Table 1: Material property data used in the Finite element model [18, 19, 21]

Figure 6: Finite element mesh (the configuration with crack and optimum cut-out).

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The finite element results indicated that, compared with the standard stop-hole specimen, the stress concentration factor of specimens with optimum cut-out hole was reduced by 63% from 8.26 to 3.05. With the hybrid repair design, the stress intensity factor was further reduced to 2.21, a 73% reduction compared with the standard stop-hole specimen.

As shown in Figure 7, more plies results in lower maximum stress, however, the stress reduction rate of successive plies diminishes with only small stress reductions after the sixth ply. Thus, patch thickness was limited to 6 plies.

Employing extended length ply-drops (Figure 5) significantly reduced adhesive stress at both ends of the patch. On the other hand, since the patch does not cover the damaged area (region of load path discontinuity), adhesive stress is low in the central region of the patch. The finite element modelling results confirms the stress state is non critical in the adhesive layer and laminate before ultimate failure of the aluminium plate.

By applying a simple cubic law [20], the fatigue life for crack re-initiation is estimated to be 20 and 52 times longer using optimum cut-out and hybrid repair configurations, respectively, compared to standard stop-hole specimens.

As recorded in Table 2 and summarised in Table 3, the fatigue tests confirmed the significant extension of fatigue initiation life. 28 and 53 times of extensions were achieved for the optimum cut-out hole and hybrid repairs, which are more significant than those estimated using the simple cubic rule.

The results also indicated that, for stop drill and optimum cut-out configurations, once crack growth reinitiated, its progression was relatively fast. In the case of the hybrid repair specimen the crack growth rate was significantly slower, which was clearly due to stress reduction of the region ahead of the crack tip, resulting from load bypass through the patch.

Figure 7. Maximum principal stress at edge of optimised hole

Specimen Type	Crack Re-initiation (flight hrs)	Average (standard deviation)	Ultimate Failure (flight hrs)	Average (standard deviation)	No Failure (flight hrs)
Cracked	N/A	N/A	17,039	15,315 (1,595)	N/A
			13,893		
Stop Drill	15,929	14,902 (1,453)	33,033	32,691 (2,712)	N/A
			30,851		
			36,393		
			30,486		
Optimum Cut	361,740	418,458 (195,374)	375,140	434,339 (196,554)	N/A
			367,755		
			443,613		
			228,281		
			756,906		
Hybrid Repair	run-out	N/A	N/A	N/A	1,713,738
	793,000		936,681		
	run-out		N/A		1,164,304

Table 2: Measured fatigue life of test specimens

Specimen type	Normalised Fatigue Life*	
	Crack Re-initiation	Ultimate Failure
Cracked	N/A	1.03
Stop Hole	1.00	2.19
Optimum Hole	28.1	29.1
Hybrid Repair	>53.2**	>62.9**

* Normalised against crack re-initiation fatigue life of the specimen with standard stop-hole

** Crack initiation and failure observed in one specimen, other two stopped at 78 and 115 nominal lifetimes without initiation.

Table 3: Normalized fatigue life of test specimens

4 CONCLUSIONS

The effectiveness of hybrid repair, an optimum cut-out hole plus bonded boron/epoxy patches, was demonstrated by comparing it with other three specimen configurations, namely, specimens with a crack, a crack and standard stop-hole, and a crack with an optimum cut-out hole. In the hybrid repair design, the patch is positioned adjacent and some distance away from the optimised cut-out. A feature of this patch repair design is that potential crack re-occurrence/ growth in the parent structure can be monitored without the patch concealing the area.

Finite element modelling results indicated that, compared with the standard stop-hole specimen, the stress concentration factor of specimens with optimum cut-out hole and hybrid repairs was reduced by 63% and 73% respectively. Based on a simple cubic law, the fatigue life for crack re-initiation was estimated to be 20 and 52 times longer respectively resulted from these reductions.

The experimentally measured results confirmed significant extension of fatigue life from the optimum cut-out (28 lifetimes) and hybrid repair (53 lifetimes), more significant than those estimated using the simple cubic rule.

The experimental results further confirmed that for the stop drill and optimum cut-out configurations, once the crack growth reinitiated, its progression was relatively fast, whilst in the case of hybrid repair specimens the crack growth rate was significantly slower.

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